

DESIGNING RESILIENCE IN TIMES OF DISRUPTION: ALIGNING SERVICE DESIGN AND DIGITAL TWINS FOR EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Disasters, climate crises, and infrastructure failures increasingly reshape the conditions under which people inhabit their environments, often producing displacement and unequal exposure to harm. In this context, Emergency Management (EM) is shifting from a reactive, risk-based model toward resilience-oriented strategies that prioritise mitigation and preparedness. Digital Twins (DTs), dynamic virtual representations that link real-time data to simulation and predictive modelling, are increasingly positioned within this shift because they support faster situational awareness and more informed decisions under uncertainty. At the same time, the ways DTs represent people and distribute visibility across communities remain underexamined, raising questions about care, participation, and whose living conditions are prioritised during crises.

This paper reviews how DTs are applied in EM and what this implies for human representation and participation. It addresses three research questions: how DTs operate across application systems and emergency phases, who DTs are built for, how humans are represented and involved, and how Service Design thinking can be aligned with Digital Twin development for Emergency Management. A structured literature review was conducted following PRISMA guidelines across Google Scholar and Scopus for publications from 2020 to 2025, resulting in a final sample of 30 studies.

The analysis identifies five main application systems: Urban Systems, Infrastructure Systems, Healthcare Systems, Fire Safety Systems, and Natural Hazard Systems, spanning mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery. Across these systems, DTs function as decision-support technologies that combine real-time data with simulation to support evacuation planning, cascading infrastructure analysis, epidemic forecasting, wildfire monitoring, structural safety assessment, and resource allocation. Case studies show measurable operational value, including good usability for railway emergency deployment and 87% prediction accuracy in earthquake damage modelling, which indicates the growing technical maturity of DT applications in crisis contexts.

The review also reveals a strong institutional orientation. Across the 30 reviewed studies, 26 were coded as institution-oriented in terms of primary users, including authorities, emergency managers, and planners. Human actors are represented mainly through behavioural models, demographic and mobility data, social sensing, or crowdsourced reporting, while co-design remains limited.

To address this gap, the paper proposes a Service Design Alignment Framework for Digital Twins in Emergency Management. The framework aligns Service Design Thinking with Digital Twin development through six phases: Research, Ideation, Prototyping, Digital Twin Development, Interface Development, and Testing. It also specifies the roles of Service Designers, Engineers and Developers, and Public Service Stakeholders across the process. In this framework, Service Designers lead the first three phases by defining context, stakeholders, needs, scenarios, and early prototypes. Engineers and Developers lead the fourth and fifth phases by building the Digital Twin and its decision-support interfaces. Public Service Stakeholders participate throughout, with stronger collaborative involvement in the design phases and testing. The paper argues that aligning Service Design with Digital Twin development helps move DTs in EM beyond a purely managerial logic toward a more explicit socio-technical process that better integrates participation and situated knowledge.

Key Words: Disaster Management¹, Digital Transition², Human-Centred Design³, Stakeholder Participation⁴

1 INTRODUCTION

Climate crises, pandemics, and infrastructural failures increasingly reshape the conditions under which people inhabit their environments. In this context, resilience is no longer understood solely as the protection of assets, but as the capacity of communities to sustain life, care, and collective agency under stress. Emergency Management (EM) is therefore shifting from a reactive, risk-based model toward resilience-oriented strategies that prioritise mitigation and preparedness (Yu et al., 2025).

Digital technologies are becoming central to how cities anticipate and simulate crises that affect the habitability of urban environments.

Among these technologies, Digital Twins (DTs) have emerged as key tools for creating dynamic virtual representations of physical entities that integrate real-time data with simulation and predictive modelling. In EM contexts, DTs are applied to evacuation modelling (Haghshenas et al., 2025), multi-agency coordination (Wolf et al., 2022), cascading infrastructure analysis (Martini et al., 2025), epidemic transmission simulation (Lin et al., 2024), and seismic damage prediction (Korkmaz et al., 2025). These developments indicate the growing technical maturity of DTs in managing crises that directly affect how cities remain inhabitable.

However, important gaps remain. Most DTs are designed primarily for institutional decision-makers rather than communities. Human representation is often reduced to behavioural modelling, demographic datasets, or social sensing inputs (Fan et al., 2021; Lin et al., 2024), while participatory development processes are rare. Although usability and human-computer interaction are increasingly acknowledged (Brucherseifer et al., 2021; Zheng et al., 2025), questions of collective care and community agency remain underexamined. If DTs increasingly shape evacuation strategies and recovery planning, they also influence whose needs are made visible and whose living conditions are prioritised for protection.

The study examines how Digital Twins are applied across different application systems and emergency phases, who their primary users are, and how human actors are represented and involved within these systems. Particular attention is given to identifying gaps in human representation and participatory development in current Digital Twin practices. Building on these findings, the paper introduces a Service Design (SD) perspective to explore how human-centred and participatory design approaches can reframe Digital Twin development.

2 BACKGROUND

2.1 Emergency Management

The Emergency Management discipline seeks to create and apply knowledge about what people and organisations can do to diminish the frequency and impact of disasters. Disasters are defined as destructive events that occur when a hazard (natural, technological, or anthropogenic agents like earthquakes or industrial explosions) interacts with human vulnerability (people's susceptibility based on factors like geographic location, level of preparedness, and income) (McEntire, 2021). Emergency managers are public servants who work with multiple stakeholders and build capabilities to deal with disasters. Such activities are described in the four EM phases, developed by the National Governors' Association in 1979:

1. Mitigation: risk reduction and loss minimization, such as land-use/building planning and insurance.
2. Preparedness: increasing readiness for a disaster, such as the creation of laws and ordinances, the acquisition of grants or other resources, and training and community education. The Mitigation and Preparedness phases are priorities in the EM profession today, extending beyond an exclusive focus on first responders (police, fire, and emergency medical personnel).
3. Response: actions taken immediately before, during, or directly after an emergency to save lives and minimize property damage, like warning people of severe weather, evacuating, sheltering, providing emergency medical care and information, and managing the arrival of donations and volunteers.
4. Recovery: returning and improving vital life support, such as repairing homes and infrastructure.

2.2 Service Design

Service Design is a field focused on developing coherent experiences using a synergy of intangible and tangible media. Six core principles define SD (Stickdorn et al., 2018): human-centered (focus on the stakeholders' perspective), collaborative (engagement of stakeholders), iterative (exploratory and adaptive approach), sequential (service as time-based sequences of interactions), real (researched and prototyped in reality), and holistic (consideration of the broader service environment and organisational context).

The Service Design Thinking process is usually structured in four phases. Initially, the Research phase helps to understand people and their behaviors in relation to a service. During the Ideation phase, designers co-develop concepts with stakeholders. This is followed by the Prototyping phase, which is conducted to explore how people might behave in future service situations through testing different aspects of a new concept, and the Implementation phase, which moves into production and rollout through change management and product development (Stickdorn et al., 2018).

In the Public Sector, the Service Design capacities are divided into four areas (Mager et al., 2016): stakeholder engagement (fostering collaborative environments), training and capacity building (equipping public stakeholders with the specialized skills and mindset needed to sustain innovation), cultural and organisational change (transforming existing cultures by embedding human-centered principles and iterative development into government practice), and policy design (adding practical experimentation and user insights into policymaking).

3 METHODOLOGY

To examine how Digital Twins are applied in Emergency Management, a structured literature review was conducted following the PRISMA guidelines (Figure 1). The review focuses on applied implementations to maintain a practice-oriented perspective.

Figure 1: PRISMA flow diagram (Authors, 2026)

Two databases were consulted: Google Scholar and Scopus. The search was conducted between December 2025 and April 2026 and limited to publications from 2020 to 2025. The following queries were used: “emergency management” AND “digital twin” in Google Scholar, and TITLE-ABS-KEY (“emergency management” AND “digital twin”) in Scopus. A total of 171 records were identified (Google Scholar n = 75; Scopus n = 96).

After removing duplicates (n = 3), 168 records were screened through title, abstract, and keyword review. Studies were included if they (1) explicitly addressed Emergency Management or disaster-related contexts, (2) described a Digital Twin, framework, or application, and (3) provided sufficient detail to analyse DT use, stakeholders, or human involvement. Studies were excluded if they were conceptual or predominantly technical (e.g., algorithmic or modelling-focused) without demonstrating a concrete application in an Emergency Management context. Following this process, 141 records were excluded, resulting in a final sample of 30 studies (Google Scholar n = 25; Scopus n = 5).

The selected studies were analysed using a structured coding approach to enable comparison across heterogeneous sources. Each paper was examined in terms of

application system, emergency phase (mitigation, preparedness, response, recovery), primary users, and forms of human representation and involvement.

The reviewed papers are predominantly published in engineering and technology journals (19), followed by disaster and environmental sciences (5), healthcare and public health (3), and information management or interdisciplinary publications (3), indicating a strong technical orientation of the field.

The literature review covers the following research questions (RQ):

RQ1: How are Digital Twins applied in Emergency Management across different application systems and emergency phases?

RQ2: Who are the primary users of Digital Twins in Emergency Management, and how are human actors represented and involved?

RQ3: How can Service Design thinking be aligned with Digital Twin development for Emergency Management?

The investigation of RQ3 builds upon both the analysed Digital Twin literature that reveals gaps in human representation and participatory development, and an earlier literature review on Service Design applications in Emergency Management (Ershova et al., 2026). RQ1 is summarised in Tables 1 and 2, while RQ2 is presented in Table 3. RQ3 is illustrated in Figure 6, which represents the Service Design Alignment Framework for Digital Twins in Emergency Management.

4 LITERATURE REVIEW IN DIGITAL TWINS FOR EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT

The concept of creating a digital counterpart of physical entities has evolved over the past two decades alongside advances in sensing, connectivity, and computational modelling. Early formulations, such as “Mirrored Spaces Model” (Grieves, 2005), described the interaction between a real space, a virtual space, and the data flow connecting them within Product Lifecycle Management. The term Digital Twin was later popularised by NASA around 2010 to simulate and monitor complex aerospace structures (Singh et al., 2021). Today, a Digital Twin approach is understood as a digital replica that gives a certain degree of intelligence and agency to the entity being twinned (Agrawal, Fischer, & Singh, 2022). The relationship can be compared to the human body: sensors act as senses that perceive the environment; the digital model functions like a brain that processes information and supports decision-making; and actuators enable feedback from the digital to the physical entity, similar to muscles executing actions (Figure 2). The Urban Digital Twin Development framework for Sustainable Solutions, including Emergency Management, follows the next phases: Data Collection, Data Integration and Processing, Creation of the Urban Digital Twin, Continuous Data Flow,

Analysis and Modelling, Decision Support, Implementation of Sustainable Solutions, and Feedback Loop (Mazzetto, 2024).

Figure 2: Digital Twin definition (Authors, 2026)

4.1 Application Systems of Digital Twins for Emergency Management

To address how Digital Twins are applied in Emergency Management across different application systems and emergency phases (RQ1), the literature review begins by identifying the main application systems that describe the operational contexts in which DTs are implemented for EM. It then examines the functions attributed to Digital Twins within mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery phases, followed by an analysis of representative case studies and technical characteristics (dataset, digital infrastructure, and interface). Selected papers discuss five Digital Twin application systems in Emergency Management, highlighting their specific functions and features across different risk contexts, represented in the following paper focus list:

1. Urban Systems (9 papers) represent multi-hazard twins that operate at the city scale and monitor natural and human-caused hazards (daily operational failures, accidents, and unspecified disruptions). Specifically, the papers' focus is: (1) urban evacuation dynamics (Haghshenas et al., 2025); (2) supporting multi-agency incident management (Wolf et al., 2022); (3) improving urban critical infrastructure resilience (Brucherseifer et al., 2021); such as (4) water distribution networks (Dui et al., 2025); (5) integrating artificial and human intelligence (Fan et al., 2021); (6) community management (Ford & Wolf, 2020); (7) distributed co-simulation approach (Martini et al., 2025); (8) human involvement in DTs (Cámara & Burgueño, 2025); (9) optimal DT display color selection (Shao & Zhang, 2025).

2. Infrastructure Systems (6 papers) capture multi-hazard twins at the facility scale and monitor natural and human-caused hazards (building collapses, tunnel accidents, and social security incidents). Namely, they highlight: (1) EM during four phases (Cheng et al., 2023); (2) safety analysis and risk assessment of structures (Zio & Miqueles, 2024); (3) multi-scenario emergency of railway passenger stations (Wang et al., 2024); (4), (5) crowd recognition technology (Jia et al., 2025; Casadei et al., 2024); (6) BIM and crowd sensing for evacuation routing (Rashidian & Malek, 2026).
3. Healthcare Systems (5 papers) reflect public health emergency twins functioning at the institutional and population level and manage epidemic transmission and influenza outbreaks. Specifically: (1) EM during four phases (Sun et al., 2025); (2) EM according to individual, hospital, and public levels (Zheng et al., 2025); (3) emergency care (Olawade et al., 2025); (4) EM for central and local government, and grassroots communities during pandemic (Zhihong et al., 2020); (5) multi-scale simulation for urban epidemic transmission (Lin et al., 2024).
4. Fire Safety Systems (3 papers) twins correspond to fire-related emergency twins at the environment and building scale, targeting explosions, toxic releases, and wildfires, in particular: (1) wildland fire management (Li et al., 2024); (2) user acceptance of virtual reality technology (Kwok et al., 2021); (3) similarity-based hybrid modelling (Yun et al., 2022).
5. Natural Hazard Systems (7 papers) denote environmental emergency twins deployed at the multi-scale, covering earthquake, flood, hurricane, and other climate risks, specifically: (1) post-disaster DT prototype (Doğan et al., 2021); (2) components and features explained with a three-dimensional DT model (Ghaffarian, 2025); (3) emergency preparedness (Akter et al., 2025); (4) flooding EM (Ge & Qin, 2024); (5) AI, blockchain, and DT (Karaduman, 2025); (6) unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) and DT (Qadir et al., 2025); (7) specific case of DT Cayirova (Korkmaz et al., 2025).

Tables 1 and 2 underline the main objects and functions of Digital Twins in Emergency Management phases for each application system. DTs support decision-making by combining real-time data with simulation. At the city level, they represent interconnected infrastructures and community networks to improve management (Ford & Wolf, 2020). Depending on the context, a DT may model a whole city, a single infrastructure asset, a hospital network (Zheng et al., 2025), or a hazard process such as flooding or earthquake damage (Doğan et al., 2021).

Table 1 Digital Twin object for each application system

Application System	Digital Twin object
Urban Systems	City, critical infrastructure (water, food, and energy supply, transportation, telecommunication, healthcare), water distribution network, category 1 emergency services, community
Infrastructure Systems	Building, e.g., railway passenger station, tunnel, material, machine, crowd
Healthcare Systems	City, public healthcare, hospital, individual (patient)
Fire Safety Systems	Environment, wildfire
Natural Hazard Systems	City, municipality, civil infrastructure, and emergency service, disaster, e.g., flood

The case studies demonstrate measurable impact across the identified application systems. In Urban Systems, a Digital Twin framework integrating gas, power, water, telecommunications, building damage, and emergency response modules was developed to simulate cascading failures and uncover indirect vulnerabilities (Martini et al., 2025). A further study demonstrated how a Digital Twin can coordinate multiple emergency services by dynamically reassessing affected transport routes during an incident (Wolf et al., 2022). At the urban flood scale, a City Flooding Digital Twin supports real-time visual situational awareness and interactive decision-making (Ge & Qin, 2024).

Within Infrastructure Systems, a multi-scenario emergency Digital Twin was implemented at the Qinghe railway passenger station and evaluated using the System Usability Scale, achieving a good usability score that indicates suitability for operational emergency deployment (Wang et al., 2024).

In Healthcare Emergency, a multi-scale urban simulation model was applied to represent epidemic transmission and support public health planning (Lin et al., 2024).

In a fire emergency, a VR-based Digital Twin environment was developed for crisis training under different emergency scenarios, strengthening preparedness through immersive simulation (Kwok et al., 2021).

Finally, in Natural Hazard Systems, an earthquake Digital Twin developed for the Çayırova district in Türkiye predicted that approximately 18% of mid-rise reinforced concrete buildings would experience minor to moderate structural damage under simulated seismic conditions and achieved 87% prediction accuracy when compared with observed damage data (Korkmaz et al., 2025).

Table 2 Application of Digital Twins in Emergency Management Phases

Application System	DT function: Mitigation & Preparedness phase	DT function: Response phase	DT function: Recovery phase
Urban Systems	Simulation of evacuation scenarios, Modelling cascading infrastructure interdependencies, Policy evaluation and investment planning, Real-time infrastructure monitoring and anomaly detection, Community condition data collection for proactive evacuation, Crowd behaviour prediction	Real-time monitoring, Damage reporting to improve first responder deployment, Multi-service coordination and route reassessment, Evacuation route optimisation, Intelligent control and resource scheduling	Identification of rebuilding bottlenecks and resource allocation, Scenario replay and retrospective analysis, Risk development database, System optimisation and adaptive planning

<p>Infrastruc- ture Systems</p>	<p>Lifecycle reinforcement and safety analysis, Hazard factor and occupational risk modelling, Virtual training and emergency decision simulation</p>	<p>Real-time infrastructure condition assessment, Resource allocation optimisation, Evacuation modelling</p>	<p>Cross-sector collaboration, Multi-scenario emergency drills, Organisational learning and resilience strengthening</p>
<p>Healthcare Systems</p>	<p>Epidemic forecasting and proactive disease prevention, Multi-scale epidemic transmission simulation, Digital platform and data model optimisation, Training and preparedness exercises</p>	<p>Emergency department capacity prediction, Real-time patient monitoring and management, Pre-hospital emergency coordination, Trauma integration and ED optimisation, Clinical decision support and in- hospital fault prediction</p>	<p>Public health emergency coordination across governance levels, Municipal healthcare resource optimisation, Inter-community health data sharing, Rehabilitation programme planning</p>
<p>Fire Safety Systems</p>	<p>Wildfire monitoring and spread modelling, Fire risk assessment, Prescribed burning planning and risk evaluation,</p>	<p>Real-time wildfire behaviour tracking, Evacuation route modelling, Tactical emergency support optimisation</p>	<p>Post-fire accident and damage analysis, Ecological impact evaluation, Fire strategy refinement</p>

	VR-based emergency scenario training		
Natural Hazard Systems	Real-time risk assessment and scenario modelling, Emergency staff rehearsals and training, Contingency strategy development, Urban planning integration, Hazard-specific simulations: earthquake structural modelling, flood flow simulation, landslide deformation modelling	Dynamic hazard monitoring and actionable insight generation, Route optimisation and incident prioritization, Rescue team configuration recommendation, Resource demand forecasting and deployment optimisation, Reduction of economic losses	Post-disaster impact evaluation, Continuous vulnerability modelling, Long-term resilience enhancement

Next, selected papers were analyzed according to their technical characteristics: datasets, digital infrastructure, and interface (visualisation and interaction).

Digital Twins in EM rely on static or dynamic data from diverse resources to create a reliable virtual mirror of the physical world. The physical foundation integrates detailed urban infrastructure, including water distribution networks (Dui et al., 2025), power grids, and telecommunications, with critical facilities like hospitals and schools (Martini et al., 2025). These models map transportation networks (Haghshenas et al., 2025) and natural landscapes, incorporating land-use zoning, vegetation (Korkmaz et al., 2025), and real-time environmental variables such as seismic activity and rainfall (Akter et al., 2025). To maintain situational awareness, the DT fuses remote sensing imagery with "social sensing" data from platforms like Twitter (currently, X) and Facebook to identify life-threatening emergencies (Fan et al., 2021). This automated layer is supplemented by crowdsourced reports, real-time tracking of spontaneous volunteers (Martini et al., 2025), and manual data collection through field observations and community surveys (Ghaffarian, 2025). Application system-specific datasets provide granularity for specialized crises, such as public health emergency twins tracking individual vitals

(Olawade et al., 2025) and hospital resource allocation (Zheng et al., 2025), or Fire Safety Systems monitoring fuel models and wind direction (Li et al., 2024).

Digital infrastructure serves as the computational backbone, processing large-scale data to simulate emergency scenarios. Across the papers analyzed, IoT and ML/AI are the primary drivers, supported by GIS, remote sensing, and blockchain. These technologies bridge physical assets with cloud-based analytical workflows. Urban Systems rely on Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and AI to run community simulations (Haghshenas et al., 2025), using LiDAR and remote sensing to map high-fidelity environments (Ford & Wolf, 2020; Fan et al., 2021). Implementation often leverages cloud ecosystems like Microsoft Azure (Wolf et al., 2022) or automation via Python to integrate real-time traffic and hazard feeds (Martini et al., 2025). Similarly, facility-scale twins integrate IoT with BIM and GIS (Cheng et al., 2023; Rashidian & Malek, 2026), using game engines like Unity3D to model structural safety and passenger dynamics (Wang et al., 2024). Specialized application systems utilize more diverse technologies. Public health emergency twins employ distributed computing and blockchain to manage secure patient data and hospital modelling (Zheng et al., 2025). Natural Hazard System response frequently deploys mobile units, including UAVs and Drones equipped with LiDAR to inspect inaccessible terrain (Qadir et al., 2025), while wireless sensor networks track seismic and environmental changes in real-time (Korkmaz et al., 2025; Karaduman, 2025).

The interface, visualisation, and interaction layer translate complex data into actionable insights by integrating 3D models with semantic and temporal data, thereby creating a spatial-temporal structure capable of hosting functional simulations (Brucherseifer et al., 2021). Across all application systems, web and mobile applications serve as the primary platforms for interaction. These interfaces offer both 2D and 3D visualisation (Figures 4, 5), where the choice often depends on the trade-off between graphic depth (3D) and the processing speed required for real-time field use (2D) (Doğan et al., 2021). Furthermore, immersive VR/AR allows responders to navigate virtual environments before physical entry (Cheng et al., 2023; Kwok et al., 2021).

In urban and infrastructure settings, specialized tools like digital map tables and the electronic situation dashboard (Figure 3) provide a common operating picture for command centres (Martini et al., 2025). Moreover, DTs often include automatic early warning alerts for structural risks (Figure 5) (Wang et al., 2024; Casadei et al., 2024). Healthcare Systems prioritize decision support through real-time treatment recommendations and colour-coded 3D city maps for epidemic tracking (Lin et al., 2024). Similarly, Fire emergency interfaces focus on real-time situational alerts and remote monitoring to guide emergency operations (Li et al., 2024). Natural Hazard System interfaces utilize extended reality (XR) to visualize seismic or flood risks, allowing users to toggle between disaster scenarios via web-based dashboards (Ghaffarian, 2025; Ge & Qin, 2024).

Figure 3: Variations on interfaces: Digital Map Table (Fraunhofer, n.d.)

Figure 4: Interface with 2D visualisation of volunteer-reported water levels (Martini et al., 2025)

Figure 5: Interfaces with 3D visualisation of fire scenario (Wang et al., 2024)

4.2 Primary Users, Human Representation, and Involvement in Digital Twin for Emergency Management

To address who the primary users of Digital Twins in Emergency Management are, and how human actors are represented and involved (RQ2), the review systematically analyses papers with respect to identified user groups and modes of human representation (Table 3).

Across the 30 reviewed papers, 26 studies were coded as institution-oriented in terms of primary users. This category includes authorities, policymakers, emergency managers, planners, public health authorities, and command-and-control actors. Papers were classified as institution-oriented when the Digital Twin was primarily designed to support organisational decision-making, planning, coordination, monitoring, or resource allocation within formal emergency governance structures. Four papers were excluded from this category because their main focus was on first responders and frontline

practitioners, namely firefighters, police officers, clinicians, and other operational staff (Cámara & Burgueño, 2025; Kwok et al., 2021; Olawade et al., 2025; Wang et al., 2024).

Although humans are present in many DTs, their role is typically indirect. In urban and infrastructure cases, citizens contribute data through social sensing and crowdsourcing mechanisms (Fan et al., 2021; Cheng et al., 2023; Martini et al., 2025). For example, public-generated social media content is used for near real-time situational awareness (Fan et al., 2021), and volunteer reports are integrated into flood simulations to estimate damage probability (Figure 4) (Martini et al., 2025). Human-in-the-Loop machine learning further incorporates human labeling and correction into model training (Fan et al., 2021). In other cases, humans are represented through behavioural and demographic modelling. Agent-based models simulate human demand and behavioural patterns (Brucherseifer et al., 2021). Demographic, mobility, and observation data are used to model population movement (Lin et al., 2024; Jia et al., 2025). In Healthcare Systems, DTs create digital user portraits of residents using sensor-based data collection (Zhihong et al., 2020). Predictive analytics are applied to model crowd behaviour during evacuations (Haghshenas et al., 2025).

A different approach is presented by Wolf et al. (2022), who explicitly co-designed a Digital Twin prototype for multi-agency incident management. Instead of treating stakeholders merely as data providers, the authors conducted semi-structured interviews and structured requirement analyses with police, fire and rescue services, ambulance services, local authorities, the Environment Agency, and other operational actors to define their needs. The prototype was designed to address real coordination gaps identified by these stakeholders, such as a lack of shared situational awareness, inefficient communication across control centres, and the absence of real-time integrated traffic and weather data. The resulting incident process model supports joint visibility of resources, estimated time of arrival, geofencing of responder vehicles, and automated cross-agency notifications. Importantly, design was iteratively validated through stakeholder feedback before further development.

However, generally, DT development creates a clear imbalance. While Digital Twins can directly shape life-saving decisions, such as evacuation routing or resource allocation, community values are mostly translated through behavioural models, demographic data, or crowdsourced inputs rather than participatory processes. In most studies, humans act as data providers or simulated agents (Fan et al., 2021; Cheng et al., 2023; Brucherseifer et al., 2021).

At the same time, several papers get direction toward design approaches. Wolf et al. (2022) stress the need to refine feedback loops and collect deeper usability insights. Brucherseifer et al. (2021) emphasise human-centred design and carefully crafted control-centre interfaces, especially in cognitively demanding crises. In Healthcare and Fire Safety Systems, authors highlight the need for intuitive interfaces, accessibility, and interdisciplinary collaboration (Zheng et al., 2025; Li et al., 2024; Akter et al., 2025).

Nevertheless, this focus remains largely at the level of usability and service optimisation. Even iterative disaster models (Ford & Wolf, 2020) prioritise feedback structures and system dynamics rather than co-design. Thus, while human-centred design is increasingly acknowledged, meaningful community involvement in DT development for Emergency Management is still rare.

Table 3 Primary Users, Human Representation, and Involvement in Digital Twin for Emergency Management

Application System	Primary Users	Human Representation and Involvement
Urban Systems	Authorities and politicians, managers and infrastructure managers, operators, drone operators, rescuers, researchers/students, volunteers and victims, citizens	Behavioural representation via agent-based modelling, Demographic and mobility data modelling, Predictive crowd behaviour analytics, Social media data for situational awareness, Human-in-the-Loop ML feedback for model correction, Citizens perform tagging, labeling, and geolocation tasks, Smartphone-based volunteer flood reporting, Serious gaming for collaborative training, Semi-structured interviews & multi-agency workshops for requirement definition
Infrastructure Systems	Government-level managers, emergency ministry staff, construction engineers, designers, rescuers, urban-planning	Social sensing via public social media data, Crowdsourced first-hand disaster reports

	administrators, event organizers, citizens	
Healthcare Systems	Central and local government authorities, public health governance bodies, clinicians, grassroots communities, patients	Demographic data modelling, Mobility tracking, Sensor-based user portrait creation, Patient journey simulation and optimisation
Fire Safety Systems	Senior managers and policymakers, command & control center operators, training instructors, firefighters	VR-based emergency training simulations
Natural Hazard Systems	Government agencies, local authorities, emergency managers, infrastructure managers and engineers, utility providers, rescuers, NGOs, community members, citizens	Behavioural and environmental modelling, Manual surveys, field observations, and interviews, Citizen mobile reporting integration, Resilience planning considering vulnerable groups

5 SERVICE DESIGN IN DIGITAL TWINS FOR EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT

To address how Service Design thinking can be aligned with Digital Twin development for Emergency Management (RQ3), the paper introduces a framework (Figure 6). The framework focuses primarily on Urban Systems, as they bring together multiple infrastructures, hazard conditions, and institutions from different application systems within a single service environment. The framework integrates the Service Design Thinking phases of Research, Ideation, Prototyping, and Implementation (Stickdorn et al., 2018) with the Urban Digital Twin Development framework for Sustainable Solutions,

including Emergency Management: Data Collection, Data Integration and Processing, Creation of the Urban Digital Twin, Continuous Data Flow, Analysis and Modelling, Decision Support, Implementation of Sustainable Solutions, and Feedback Loop (Mazzetto, 2024).

This integration results in a six-phase process: Research, Ideation, Prototyping, Digital Twin Development, Interface Development, and Testing. The first three phases derive mainly from Service Design Thinking, while the latter three group the main stages of Digital Twin development into a more synthetic sequence. The framework also maps the involvement of three actor groups: Service Designers, Engineers and Developers, and Public Service Stakeholders. In Figure 6, for Service Designers, Engineers and Developers, short blocks indicate a support role, medium blocks indicate an implementation role, and high blocks indicate a leadership role. For Public Service Stakeholders, short blocks indicate indirect participation, medium blocks indicate participation through feedback and testing, and high blocks indicate collaborative participation (Christiansson et al., 2024).

Figure 6: Service Design Alignment Framework for Digital Twins in Emergency Management (Authors, 2026)

The description of the Service Designer role and the related case studies in the first three phases is based on prior analysis of Service Design applications in Emergency Management (Ershova et al., 2026). Within the framework, the Service Designer role includes understanding the context, mapping stakeholders and their needs and journeys, co-designing scenarios and improved journeys, co-designing and testing prototypes, advocating for users, designing visualisations, interfaces, and interactions,

and conducting tests. Their leadership role is concentrated mainly in the first three phases.

In the first phase, Research, Service Designers focus on understanding the context, mapping stakeholders, and identifying needs and journeys. This includes desk research on the historical, geographical, and organisational context of emergencies, as in studies of volcano preparedness (Van Manen et al., 2015), Alpine Fault earthquake readiness (Jaenichen et al., 2019), and emergency healthcare settings (van der Lugt and van der Laan, 2017). It also includes interviews (Starnino et al., 2016; de Mello Freire et al., 2020), surveys and questionnaires (Rice et al., 2022), and observation (Santos and Sustar, 2023). These activities produce stakeholder maps (Jeong et al., 2016), personas (McGee et al., 2021), journey maps (Rice et al., 2022), and system maps that clarify which actors, needs, and service conditions should inform Digital Twin modelling.

In the second phase, Ideation, Service Designers focus on co-designing scenarios and improving journeys. This phase translates research findings into future service concepts, value propositions, and scenario-based representations of emergencies. Relevant methods include workshops and dot voting (Van Manen et al., 2015) or ideation through design cards (Haines-Gadd et al., 2015). Scenario development has been used to reframe mental health support (Van der Bijl-Brouwer and Watson, 2015) and public preparedness (Jeong et al., 2016), while service journeys and blueprints compare current and proposed service configurations across response and recovery (Yu et al., 2025). In the framework, this phase defines Digital Twin scenarios (use cases) and journeys of interaction with the Digital Twin.

In the third phase, Prototyping, Service Designers focus on co-designing and testing prototypes. This phase turns scenarios into tangible service propositions, touchpoints, and early interface ideas before full technical development. Prior studies use service roleplay (Chamorro-Koc et al., 2024), interface prototyping (Pedgley and Şener, 2024), and serious games for interface testing (Radianti et al., 2018). Within the framework, this phase translates stakeholder requirements into forms that guide later technical choices.

The role of Engineers and Developers includes assessing technological possibilities, checking feasibility, developing the Digital Twin and related technologies, developing visualisations, interfaces, and interactions, and supporting testing. Their leadership role is concentrated mainly in the fourth and fifth phases.

In the fourth phase, Digital Twin Development, Engineers and Developers focus on Digital Twin development. This phase covers Data Collection, Data Integration and Processing, Creation of the Urban Digital Twin, Continuous Data Flow, Analysis and Modelling (Mazzetto, 2024), described next in connection with the literature review done before in this paper. In Urban Systems, this includes integrating infrastructures, building damage, and emergency response modules into one Digital Twin environment (Martini et al., 2025). In Infrastructure Systems, technical development combines BIM, GIS, IoT,

and real-time sensing data (Cheng et al., 2023; Rashidian & Malek, 2026) to model structural safety and evacuation processes (Wang et al., 2024). In Healthcare Systems, technical development supports epidemic transmission modelling (Lin et al., 2024), hospital data integration, and public health planning (Zheng et al., 2025). In Natural Hazard Systems, Engineers and Developers use UAVs (Qadir et al., 2025), wireless sensor networks and seismic modelling (Korkmaz et al., 2025), and flood modelling (Ge and Qin, 2024) to generate dynamic risk assessments.

In the fifth phase, Interface Development, Engineers and Developers focus on Decision Support (Mazzetto, 2024). This phase corresponds mainly to decision support and translates Digital Twin outputs into usable forms for interpretation, coordination, and action. Across the reviewed studies, this includes web and mobile applications and 2D and 3D visualisations (Doğan et al., 2021) and immersive VR or AR environments (Kwok et al., 2021). Urban and infrastructure cases include digital map tables and electronic situation dashboards for command centres and multi-agency coordination (Martini et al., 2025).

Public Service Stakeholders, including authorities, operators, policymakers, and citizens, participate across both the Service Design and Digital Twin development phases. In the first three design phases, their participation is more collaborative. They contribute contextual knowledge and take part in interviews, workshops, journey mapping, and co-design activities, as shown in cases with Emergency Department staff (McGee et al., 2021), patients and recovery participants (Rice et al., 2022), and collaborative scenario building (Van der Bijl-Brouwer and Watson, 2015). In the later technical phases, participation becomes more selective. Stakeholders provide data, volunteer flood reports, and local observations (Martini et al., 2025).

The sixth phase, Testing, actively brings together all three actor groups through Implementation of Sustainable Solutions, and Feedback Loop (Mazzetto, 2024). Service Designers facilitate testing activities, Engineers and Developers support technical validation and system adjustment, and Public Service Stakeholders test interfaces (Wang et al., 2024), and give feedback on usability and coordination needs (Brucherseifer et al., 2021). This phase includes the evaluation of prototypes and interfaces and the refinement of the broader socio-technical arrangement through feedback on coordination and usability.

6 CONCLUSION

This paper examined the role of Digital Twins in Emergency Management through three research questions, moving from current applications to user orientation and, finally, to the contribution of Service Design. The review shows that Digital Twins are already applied across a broad range of Emergency Management contexts and are no longer limited to isolated technical experiments. Across the reviewed studies, they are used in Urban Systems, Infrastructure Systems, Healthcare Systems, Fire Safety Systems, and

Natural Hazard Systems, and they support activities across mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery. Their main contribution lies in linking real-time data, simulation, and predictive modelling in ways that strengthen decision support under conditions of uncertainty. The analysed case studies show that this can improve evacuation planning, infrastructure monitoring, epidemic forecasting, wildfire tracking, structural safety assessment, and coordination between emergency actors. In this sense, the literature confirms both the growing technical maturity of Digital Twins and the expansion of their application scope within crisis contexts.

At the same time, the review shows that current Digital Twin practice in Emergency Management remains strongly institution-oriented. Most systems are designed primarily for authorities, emergency managers, infrastructure operators, planners, public health bodies, and command-and-control settings, while communities and frontline actors are less often positioned as central participants in development. Human representation is usually indirect and mediated through behavioural models, demographic and mobility data, social sensing, or crowdsourced inputs. This means that people often appear in Digital Twins as data points, categories, or simulated behaviour rather than as situated actors with lived experience, practical knowledge, and different capacities to act under stress. Although some studies acknowledge usability, human-centred interfaces, and interdisciplinary collaboration, co-design remains limited. This imbalance matters because Digital Twins increasingly influence how risks are visualised, how priorities are set, and how emergency action is coordinated. They therefore shape not only operational decisions, but also the visibility of needs and the distribution of care during crises.

The main contribution of the paper lies in the response to RQ3. Rather than treating Service Design as an external set of methods added to an existing technical process, the paper proposes a Service Design Alignment Framework for Digital Twins in Emergency Management. The framework aligns Service Design Thinking with Digital Twin development through six phases: Research, Ideation, Prototyping, Digital Twin Development, Interface Development, and Testing. This structure clarifies how different forms of expertise can contribute across the process. In the first three phases, Service Designers take a leading role in understanding context, mapping stakeholders, identifying needs and journeys, defining scenarios, and testing early service and interface concepts. In the fourth and fifth phases, Engineers and Developers lead the construction of the Digital Twin, including data integration, modelling, and the development of interfaces for decision support. Public Service Stakeholders participate throughout the framework, with stronger collaborative involvement in the early phases and testing.

This framework responds directly to the gap identified in the review. It translates the general call for more human-centred Digital Twins into a staged development process that specifies who is involved, when they are involved, and how their contribution relates to the overall system. In this way, Service Design does not replace engineering development, but complements it by introducing methods for problem framing,

stakeholder articulation, journey-based reasoning, co-design, prototyping, and situated feedback. The framework, therefore, repositions Digital Twin development as a socio-technical process in which technical modelling, institutional decision-making, and lived experience are brought into closer relation.

The paper has several limitations. The review covers a relatively small body of applied studies published between 2020 and 2025 and is shaped by the available literature, which is itself strongly technical and institution-oriented. The proposed framework is conceptual and literature-based, and it has not yet been validated through direct application in a live Digital Twin project. Future research should therefore test the framework in practice, examine how it performs across different Emergency Management contexts, and refine its phases, outputs, and evaluation criteria through empirical case work. Even so, the study shows that the future relevance of Digital Twins in Emergency Management depends not only on data quality, modelling capacity, and interface performance, but also on how these systems are designed, by whom, and for whom.

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